

Annual report CAA Netherlands-Flanders chapter (CAA-NLFL)

Board:

Chair: Ronald Visser

Secretary: Jitte Waagen

Treasurer: Devi Taelmans

During the annual CAA meeting in Oslo various people from the CAA-NLFL chapter were present and contributed with various papers.

On November 24–25, 2016 we held our annual meeting. This year it was a joint meeting with CAA-DE. Nearly 75 people participated and enjoyed 22 presentations. The subjects we dealt with were the Statistical Analysis / Network Analysis in Archaeology, Archival and Management of (3D) Archaeological Data, Digital Archaeology and the Wider Public, and Remote Sensing and Landscape Archaeology. The presentations were generally of high quality and interesting discussions arose, including a continuation of a discussion on clustering that started in the previous joint meeting in Cologne in 2014. The meeting was also preceded by a 4hr-workshop on LiDAR applications in archaeology where 20 participants were introduced to technical aspects, visualization techniques and archaeological applications of LiDAR-data. Our annual meeting has cost € 1815.25. The paying participants have paid a total of € 1894.08, leading to a positive balance of € 78.83, which will be used for the maintenance of our website.

During the meeting we Erwin Meylemans retreated from the board and we will continue with a board of three.